

The Impact of the Publishing Business on the Effectiveness of Scientific Research

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Abstract

Recent years have seen a significant and measurable decline—by approximately 90%—in breakthrough scientific research output. This article examines the critical role of commercial publishers in this trend, highlighting how they control access to knowledge, impose barriers to non-conventional works, and distort scientific value through enforced citation and impact factor metrics. The emerging conflict between the goals of science (knowledge development) and publishing businesses (profit maximization) is analyzed. Particular attention is given to the harmful role of editorial pre-peer review processes, which filter out original research before it reaches qualified reviewers. Solutions are proposed, including abolishing editorial pre-review, limiting publisher monopolies, and restoring control over scientific communication to the research community.

Keywords

Scientific research decline, Commercial publishing, Pre-peer review, Research evaluation metrics, Impact factor, Open science reform

Main Text

There has been a significant decline in the number of breakthrough scientific achievements in science in recent years. In 2023, a group of scientists from the American University of Minnesota, using material including more than 45 million scientific articles and 3.9 million patents published in countries around the world over the past sixty years, showed that the decline in the number of significant scientific research was about 90% [3, p. 138]. The current situation makes the analysis of factors influencing the effectiveness of scientific research particularly relevant.

A scientific article is the main product of a scientist's work. An analysis of the scientific literature and periodicals market has shown that the five largest publishing houses – Elsevier, Wiley, Taylor & Francis, Sage and Springer (science) – today control over 50% of the scientific world and this share is constantly growing [3, p. 1]. All of these commercial companies have huge sales and their profit margins are around 40% – higher than Apple, Google or Amazon [1].

This situation creates challenges for the scientific community, since the commercial interests of publishers lead to a conflict with the need for free access to scientific knowledge. The desire of publishers to maximize the profitability of their work leads to an increase in the prices of journal subscriptions, which prevents researchers from accessing the necessary information and databases.

Scientific publishers manage to avoid most of the real costs. They often avoid significant publishing expenses, since most scientific articles are provided to them almost free of charge by scientists who carry out research and write articles at their own expense or at the expense of government funding. Publishers derive significant benefits from the work of scientists without investing significant funds. Many universities and scientific organizations refuse to pay too expensive subscriptions. As a result, scientists, institutes and government organizations become dependent on commercial publishers for access to scientific information, which slows down progress in scientific research. Usually, this circumstance is the only analysis of the impact of the publishing business on processes in the scientific community. It is necessary to study in more detail the processes of interaction between the scientific community and the publishing business.

As an object of analysis, we will choose two top journals with a high impact factor, Nature and Science. These publishers are considered the standard that determines the level of scientific work. Let us consider the impact of detailed templates of publishers on scientific development when researchers submit material: the lack of the opportunity to submit unauthorized works, recommendations on the number of authors and references, the use of publication metrics, the inclusion of intermediate stages of processing articles before they are transferred to reviewers. Detailed templates, the implementation of which certain publishers require from researchers when submitting articles, limit the creativity of authors and affect the originality and significance of the proposed material [2, p. 103]. An overly detailed template is proposed in such a well-known journal as Nature, where strict adherence to the prescribed structural parameters restrains diversity and innovation in the submitted research, leads to a limitation of creative expression and the evaluation of innovative ideas. The journal Science does not provide for the possibility of submitting unauthorized works. The submission procedure itself assumes that a specific article has several or even many dozens of authors. However, submitting original work is an important aspect of scientific activity, as it contributes to the development of new concepts and approaches to solving scientific problems. The history of science contains many examples of breakthrough ideas proposed by a single author. In many scientific journals, an excessive number of references (many dozens) to an article is considered acceptable. However, an excessive number of references in an article may be the result of compilation. The presence of many references without proper verification can lead to a decrease in the author's originality and scientific level of the work. When writing scientific articles, the quality and relevance of sources should remain a priority, and it is necessary to balance the number of references so as to support the argumentation of the research and maintain its author's originality.

Publication metrics are currently used to evaluate almost every scientific work. However, criteria such as the number of publications, the number of citations, and

the impact factor are not an exhaustive set for an objective assessment of the value of a scientific publication. The adopted publication metrics may be subject to various limitations and influences of publishing policies, which may distort the real value of scientific work.

Impact factors may be influenced by publishers, since the assessment of this indicator depends on the number of citations of articles published in a particular journal and may be distorted if the publisher artificially increases the number of citations using various methods.

Qualitative assessment of scientific papers cannot be completely reduced to numerical metrics. It requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account not only the number of publications and citations, but also the significance and originality of the presented ideas, methods, and research results. Critical thinking, expert opinion, and peer review play an important role in an objective assessment of the scientific value of the work. The most significant impact on the effectiveness of published scientific materials is the fact that in a number of peer-reviewed journals there are intermediate stages of processing articles before they are sent to reviewers. These stages often include an assessment of the compliance of the submitted article with the formal requirements of the journal, such as structure, formatting, compliance with citation rules, etc. Such procedures are also used in Nature and Science journals. Articles that do not meet the requirements of the publishers may be recognized as "not in format" or "not in line with the journal's policy" and, accordingly, rejected without being sent to reviewers. This creates restrictions for researchers, since the editors impose certain standards that may be more related to the interests and advantages of the journal itself than to scientific research. It is this circumstance that obviously largely determines the sharp and progressive decline in the effectiveness of scientific research. This is where the conflict of interests of the publishing business and the need for effective scientific development manifests itself. In fact, by now a publishing and scientific corporation has been formed, managed and operating in the interests of publishers, whose main goal is to make a profit. At the same time, a balanced system has been built that uses society's desire for new scientific knowledge in its own interests. The publishing business, using the preferences received by scientific organizations and often the selfless enthusiasm of the scientific community, has provided itself with the opportunity to receive huge superprofits. The system is focused on obtaining the appearance of a scientific achievement within the framework of the marketing approach, demonstrating intense and "productive" activity. Automation within such a system is aimed at reducing the publishers' costs of processing the flow of scientific articles. This is served by publication metrics and the required strict formats for presenting the material. The recommendation to have a large number of authors and a number of references in published articles is aimed at attracting as many potential buyers as possible of the product being sold - scientific articles at an extremely inflated price. Stimulation of a constant large flow of articles proposed for publication by researchers is ensured by including the number of publications, citations and the impact factor of the journal in the assessment of the qualifications of each scientist and his productivity. Moreover, all these indicators are determined by publishers, and all costs are paid for with budgetary funds - the salaries of

scientists at their workplaces and through subscriptions to scientific libraries at the request of researchers.

The urgent need to separate scientific activity and publishing business under the managerial dominance of the scientific community has become obvious. Scientific development should become the main goal of scientific publishing. Antimonopoly measures should be taken in the field of scientific publishing business. At present, the dominance of large publishing houses in the world of scientific publication creates inequality in access to scientific knowledge and assessment of the scientific value of work. At the first stage, preliminary review of incoming works by the editors of publishing houses should be stopped. In our opinion, the catastrophic decline in breakthrough scientific achievements of recent times is largely due to this activity of publishing houses. It remains only to guess how many breakthrough works that could open up new directions in a particular field of science have not been accepted for publication recently, which has led to the observed decline in the rate of scientific development.

At the same time, it is advisable to preserve all the undoubted achievements of publishing, which must be directed to the development of science.

Literature

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